

Hypothesis - A modified very low carbohydrate ketogenic diet is an effective adjunct therapy for hepatitis C infection

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Summary

Hepatitis C Virus replication is glucose-dependent and involves the manipulation of hepatic lipid pathways by viral proteins.

Hepatic lipid pathways and serum glucose concentrations are well-researched as targets of dietary interventions.

A carbohydrate-restricted diet modulates hepatic lipid pathways and glycaemia in ways consistent with the inhibition of HCV replication and reversal of the adverse metabolic and inflammatory effects of chronic hepatitis C.

HCV cell entry is facilitated by high expression of LDL receptors, which can be downregulated by the consumption of a diet high in saturated fat, and low in 18:2 n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acid.

In the context of chronic hepatitis C and significant carbohydrate restriction a well-formulated ketogenic diet with a higher SFA/PUFA ratio will not increase cardiovascular risk.

Background

Hepatitis C virus (HCV) is a blood-borne virus which infects an estimated 150-200 million people worldwide. Chronic hepatitis C infection (CHC) is the leading reason for liver transplantation. About 343,000 deaths due to liver cancer attributed to CHC occurred in 2013, up from 198,000 in 1990. An additional 358,000 deaths in 2013 occurred due to cirrhosis.[1]

Treatment with interferon and ribavirin, the classical standard of care, usually lasts 6-12 months and is associated with relatively low viral clearance rates and a relatively high incidence of serious side effects. The recent development of combination direct-acting antiviral drugs with a high degree of specificity, a high clearance rate, a low rate of side effects, and which need only be taken for 6-8 weeks, promises to revolutionise treatment, however DAAs are currently highly-priced and, with the best will in the world, the treatment of 150-200 million people with DAAs will necessarily involve considerable waiting without treatment for the majority. Therefore, although a hypothesis suggesting that a modified ketogenic diet, a currently popular therapeutic diet with a long medical history, may be appropriate for the amelioration of CHC and as an adjunct to treatment (by lowering viral loads before treatment and decreasing symptoms that may be exacerbated by chemotherapy) may now seem redundant, the practicalities of the current situation regarding DAAs indicate that, quite apart from the academic interest of the dietary question and the clues it might offer to further developments in virology, if the diet-virus hypothesis is true the results may yet prove productive of clinical benefit.

Recently reports have emerged of liver cancer [HCC] recurrence following clearance of HCV with DAAs. This is proposed to be due to a rapid loss of HCV's pro-inflammatory immune-modulating effect.[2] In a population who achieved SVR after treatment with Interferon/ribavirin, patients with

diabetes (adjusted HR 1.88; 95% CI, 1.21 to 2.91) or HCV GT3 (adjusted HR 1.62; 95% CI, 0.96 to 2.734) were significantly more likely to develop HCC.[3] The dietary therapy proposed herein offers a method for reducing such risk by a stepped reduction in viral load pre-treatment

HCV, carbohydrate, and lipid pathways

HCV manipulates lipid pathways in hepatocytes.[4] It has long been known that diet is a potent modulator of hepatic lipid pathways, especially at extremes of fat and carbohydrate balance, or with differences in fat or carbohydrate type. HCV virion particles exit infected cells via VLDL exocytosis, in particular the triglyceride-rich lipoprotein (TRL) variant of very low density lipoprotein (VLDL), and enter uninfected cells by engagement with the LDL receptor complex. The hepatitis C virion can be seen as a Trojan horse which masquerades as a lipoprotein particle and hijacks the cholesterol transport system.[4]. High triglycerides (TG), together with low LDL cholesterol, are associated with poor response to interferon/ ribavirin therapy.[5] The pathways involved in HCV replication and virion assembly (DGAT1, triglyceride rich VLDL) are upregulated by dietary carbohydrate.[6,7]. Silencing apolipoprotein B (ApoB) messenger RNA in infected cells causes a 70% reduction in the secretion of both ApoB-100 and HCV.[8] Dietary carbohydrate increases hepatic triglyceride, which drives the secretion of ApoB and very-low-density lipoproteins (VLDLs) that are larger and triglyceride enriched. [9] Very low carbohydrate ketogenic diets (VLCKD) lower serum triglycerides and decrease TRL-VLDL. [10] The type of carbohydrate in the diet, as well as the amount, also influences triglyceride levels; in an experiment in which different sugars (85g) were fed 4 hours before a lunch, when fructose was consumed, absolute lipogenesis was 2-fold greater than when it was absent. Postlunch, serum TG were 11–29% greater and TG-rich lipoprotein-TG concentrations were 76–200% greater when 50:50 or 25:75 glucose to fructose ratios were fed instead of pure glucose (P,0.05).[11]

Fig. 6. HCV co-opts the hepatic TRL remnant pathway. After a fatty meal, there is a 26-fold increase in very-low density lipo-viral particles (LVP) which are rapidly cleared from the plasma ($t_{1/2}$ of 95 min) [77].

HCV proliferation is promoted in Huh-7.5 cells cultured at 4.5 g/L glucose, the equivalent of the blood glucose concentrations of diabetes patients, and inhibited at the normoglycaemic fasting blood glucose concentration of 1.0 g/L. This result suggests that intensive control of glucose concentrations would aid antiviral therapy in hepatitis C patients with diabetes.[12]

Normoglycaemia is attainable through carbohydrate restriction.[13,14] The post-prandial elevation of blood glucose is also avoidable by exclusion of high-carbohydrate foods. In the 2015 experiment of Nuttall et al 2015 post-prandial glucose concentrations in type 2 diabetic patients were reduced from 3 g/L to 1.5 g/L after 3 days of a carbohydrate free diet.[15]

PPAR-alpha, a hepatic transcription factor controlling fatty acid oxidation, gluconeogenesis and ketogenesis, which is upregulated by carbohydrate restriction[16,17], inhibits HCV replication.[18] The PPAR-alpha agonist naringenin, a grapefruit flavone, has been shown to have anti-HCV activity in vitro.[19]

Thus the metabolic pathways upregulated by carbohydrate restriction are predicted to inhibit replication of the hepatitis C virus.

The importance of fat type in CHC.

A higher serum LDL cholesterol in HCV cases is associated with improved response to interferon + ribavirin.[20] PCSK9 inhibits HCV cell entry and is associated with elevated LDL.[21] Higher serum LDL cholesterol is associated with very low incidence of serious liver disease in prospective observational studies designed to rule out reverse causation.[22] Statin drugs, which decrease TRL-VLDL but downregulate PCSK9, have been shown to slightly but significantly lower HCV viral load, but benefit of this can be offset by LDL-receptor upregulation.[23] Lower intakes of saturated fat result in higher expression of LDL receptors in hepatocytes.[24] Dietary saturated fat increases LDL by down-regulating LDL-receptors.[25]

Saturated fats decrease VLDL and TG in the context of a low-carbohydrate diet, but have the opposite effect when carbohydrate intake is high.[26]

Figure 1

Pathways of lipoprotein metabolism. Dietary carbohydrate increases hepatic TG that drives the secretion of very-low-density lipoproteins (VLDLs) that are larger and triglyceride (TG) enriched. These particles are rapidly lipolysed by lipoprotein lipase (LPL) to remnant lipoproteins that are then catabolized by hepatic lipase (HL) to small, dense low-density lipoprotein (LDL) particles that are less efficiently cleared from plasma, likely due to reduced LDL receptor affinity. Dietary saturated fat has been shown to preferentially increase plasma concentrations of larger LDL particles, likely by reducing their plasma clearance through suppression of LDL receptor activity, although increased hepatic secretion of their precursors may also play a role. Abbreviation: CETP, cholesteryl ester transfer protein.

2From Siri-Tarino 2015

Odd-chain saturated fatty acids which are only found in dairy fats, and short and medium-chain saturated fatty acids (C:4-14) found in dairy and coconut are associated with a decreased incidence of type 2 diabetes.[27,28]

Anecdotal reports exist of lower viral load and improvement of HCV symptoms when restricting refined and concentrated carbohydrate sources and consuming saturated fats e.g. dairy fats, coconut, including the author's own experience.[29] Evidence from a human population with CHC shows that higher PUFA and carbohydrate intakes are associated with steatosis, fibrosis staging, and poor response to therapy, but higher saturated and monounsaturated fat intakes are not.[30]

Unlike 18:2 and 18:3 polyunsaturated fats, very long chain highly unsaturated fatty acids inhibit HCV replication in cell cultures in the order DHA>AA>EPA at concentrations consistent with dietary exposures through consumption of meat, eggs, and fish.[31,32]

Other considerations favouring a modified ketogenic diet for the control of symptoms and metabolic syndromes associated with CHC.

The hyperglycaemia, steatosis, and insulin resistance which are downstream results of viral

manipulation of hepatocyte metabolism are also associated with non-alcoholic liver disease (NAFLD), which is considered to be caused by over-consumption of modern refined food diets. A classic action of insulin is to stimulate fatty acid synthesis in liver during times of carbohydrate excess.[33]

Some investigators have found a strong association between dietary carbohydrate intake and severity of both steatosis and steatohepatitis in NAFLD and its inflammatory sequel, non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH).[34,35] A ketogenic diet has been shown to be effective in the treatment of NAFLD [36]. Highly saturated fats are hepatoprotective in animal models of alcoholic liver disease and chemotoxic liver disease, whereas polyunsaturated fats increase progression of hepatitis.[37,38] Highly saturated fats are protective in the rat model of NAFLD, while fats high in linoleic acid such as corn oil or lard from corn-fed pigs are an important component of the high-fat diet (HFD) fed to rats to produce NAFLD.[39,40] Virgin coconut oil fed to 20 obese healthy human volunteers for 4 weeks (30 mL/day) resulted in lowering of ALT and AST values.[41] A low carbohydrate diet, not restricted in saturated fat, normalised GGT in type 2 diabetics with NAFLD who took part in a pilot trial. The effect of carbohydrate restriction on GGT was not correlated with weight loss.[14]

Medium chain triglycerides, concentrated forms of saturated fatty acids found in coconut oil and dairy fat (C:8-10) have been used successfully to treat jaundice in children.[42]

In a pilot study of patients with early-stage NAFLD (n=24) higher levels of eicosanoids derived from linoleic acid were positively associated with steatosis staging, and steatosis resolved completely after 6 months on a diet in which LA was restricted to 4% of energy and sugar to 10%. Though the diet was low in fat (20-35% of energy) dairy was favoured as a source of fat.[43]

Antibodies to n-6 metabolites are found in patients with HCV who drink alcohol in moderation.[44]

Hepatitis is an inflammatory condition and markers of inflammation are lowered by carbohydrate restriction.[45] A ketogenic diet improves neuroinflammation which may ameliorate the “brain fog” associated with chronic HCV infection.[46]

A note on cardiovascular safety

Chronic HCV infection is associated with hypocholesterolaemia and hypobetalipoproteinaemia as a consequence of HCV manipulation of lipid pathways, yet these conditions are not cardioprotective due to the insulin resistance produced by HCV manipulation of blood sugar and hepatic lipid regulation; cardiovascular risk correlates instead with viral load and degree of steatosis.[47] While a ketogenic diet in the context of CHC may be predicted to increase LDL cholesterol, associated with favourable effects on the course of the disease, ketogenic diets are known to decrease betalipoproteinaemia, ApoCIII, and other lipoprotein classes and LDL particle subtypes known to be associated with cardiovascular risk.[9]

Serum saturated fatty acids with even-numbered chains (C16 and C18) in serum lipids are associated with increased cardiovascular risk, however the levels of these fatty acids, which are partly produced by de novo lipogenesis, are increased by dietary carbohydrate [48], whereas the levels of odd-chain saturated fatty acids (C15 and C17), which are sourced from the diet (dairy and ruminant fats) and may also be produced endogenously by alpha-oxidation of even-chain saturated fats, are negatively associated with cardiovascular risk.[49]

Consumption of saturated fat as an independent factor is not directly associated with cardiovascular risk in population studies,[50,51] and attempts to reduce cardiovascular risk by restricting saturated fat have very limited effects even in trials where the intervention diet also includes other factors

expected to reduce cardiovascular risk.[52] In populations where full-fat dairy, including cream and butter, is the major source of saturated fat, higher saturated fat intake is associated with a reduced risk of ischemic heart disease.[53,54].

Diet and the historical epidemiology of HCV

Phylogenetic analyses using molecular clock methods estimate that the genotypes of HCV are in the region of 500–2000 years old, indicating that endemic strains have been present and circulating in human populations for centuries before the introduction of medical injections and transfusions.[55] Ancient forms of warfare (spears, swords, arrows, musket, and grapeshot) as well as pre-antiseptic medical and tattooing techniques should have been at least as effective at spreading a blood-borne virus as late 20th century injecting practice, yet (with the caveat that accurate blood testing for HCV only dates from 1991) epidemic rates of HCV infection appear to be a late-20th century phenomenon. The linoleic acid content of adipose tissue has increased by 136% over the last half century, an increase highly correlated with an increase in dietary LA intake over the same period of time.[56]

Figure 3 Increase in adipose linoleic acid in US population (from Guyenet and Carlson 2015)

The question may be asked, whether shifts in dietary macronutrient composition and a simultaneous rise in diabetes and pre-diabetes rates in the period after 1980 have made HCV spread more easily among modern populations. In particular, do the factors of lower saturated fat consumption, higher 18:2 polyunsaturated fat consumption, and higher carbohydrate consumption seen since 1980 create a metabolic gradient which favours higher viral load in the infected, and greater hepatic and immunological susceptibility to infection in the uninfected, compared to previous generations?

Discussion

Multiple lines of evidence, as discussed above, suggest that a very low carbohydrate diet in which dairy fat and coconut are major fat sources and in which polyunsaturated vegetable oils are avoided,

but not the polyunsaturated fats EPA, DHA and AA, will inhibit HCV replication, lower viral load, and reverse steatosis. For ease of compliance the diet can be modelled on that of Unwin et al.[14] The effect, if the hypothesis is correct, should be sufficiently strong that it can be tested in a short-term small n= pilot study. For example, ten people with viral load of >500,000 copies/ml placed on the diet for 21 days. Primary outcome to be tested is the viral load, secondary outcomes are QOL questionnaires, liver enzymes, blood lipids and fasting BG, and blood ketones. In a free-living population blood ketones and fasting TG/HDL ratio can be used to check compliance with the diet, but n= may need to be larger to allow subgroup analysis of adherent vs non-adherent subjects.

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